

Socio-Demographic Profile and Nutritional Assessment of Pre-School Children (Age 0-6 Years) Availing Integrated Child Development Scheme (ICDS) Services in Nandyal Rural

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Abstract:

Background: Integrated Child Development Services (ICDS) one of the world's largest early child health programme, had been launched in India in 1975 to promote integrated development of children from prenatal to six years of age. One of the major objectives of the scheme is to improve the nutritional status of children in the age group of 0-6 years through anganwadi centres. The present study is an attempt to assess the nutritional status of pre-school children in anganwadi centres in rural Nandyal.

Aims and Objectives: To study the socio-demographic profile of children availing ICDS services. 2. To assess the nutritional status of children of age group 0-72 months enrolled in Anganwadi centres.

Materials and Methods: A community-based, observational, cross-sectional study was conducted in the rural Nandyal. A total of 160 anganwadi centres were selected in rural area using epi-info software. From each Anganwadi centre, 25 children were selected by simple random sampling. Weight for Height was calculated to assess the nutritional status of children. Children who were more than 2 SD above the reference median (i.e. a Z score of more than –were considered to be normal.

Results: The present study revealed that male children are comparatively more under nourished (50.5%) than female children (47.6%). Christians are less under nourished (25%) when compared to Hindus (49.5%) and Muslims (47%). Children of illiterate mothers (50.4%) are more under nourished when compared to children of graduate and post graduate mothers (25%).

Conclusion: The study noticed that there is need for more health awareness campaigns at village level. It also reiterates the importance of female literacy in family for focusing on the nutrition aspects of children.

Keywords: Nutritional status, Pre-school children, Anganwadi centres, ICDS, Rural.

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Introduction

Early childhood (the first six years) constitutes the most crucial period in life, when the foundations are laid for cognitive, social, emotional, physical/motor development and cumulative lifelong learning. Child survival, growth and development, has to be looked at as a holistic approach, as one cannot be achieved without the others. There have to be balanced linkages between education, health and nutrition for proper development of a child.[1]

Launched on 2nd October 1975 in 33 blocks, the Integrated Child Development Services (ICDS) scheme has emerged from its small beginnings, to become India's flagship programme for the integrated development of children from prenatal to six years of age. It represents one of the world's largest and most unique programmes for early

childhood development, adopting a multi-sectoral approach to child development, incorporating health, early education and nutrition interventions. The ICDS programme functions through a network of Anganwadi Centres (AWCs) which are the focal points for the delivery of services attached to the scheme and are managed by the Anganwadi Workers (AWWs).[2]

Under the ICDS scheme, there is a provision of Supplementary Nutritious Food to the beneficiaries. Take Home Ration is given to Pregnant Women & Lactating Mothers, children (6 months - 3 years) and severely malnourished children and Hot Cooked Meals are provided to children (3 - 6 years). ICDS is a universal and a self-selecting scheme. Those who visit Anganwadi Centres and enroll themselves can avail these services.[3]

Recent evaluation of the most widely quoted Integrated Child Development Services (ICDS) programme in operation in India revealed inadequate coverage [4] and about 36 percent of the functionaries at the community level were not able to monitor growth that is essential in identifying the children in need of nutritional support. The major reasons identified for poor performance of most ICDS centre were: lack of skills in recording weight in growth charts; non-availability of growth charts; non-functioning of weighing scales, and non-cooperation of parents. [5]

There is little consensus on the success of the ICDS program in tackling problems of health and nutrition in early childhood, despite being one of the most studied health and nutrition interventions. [6] Within the public health literature, there are many quasi-experimental studies that investigate the effect of ICDS participation on specific health behaviour or conditions. In India the nationwide Integrated Child Development Services (ICDS) uses the I.A.P criteria to grade under nutrition. The current WHO recommendation is to use Z score or the standard deviation system to grade under nutrition. Although widely recommended the z scores have not been widely used in India, especially in community based studies. There are many studies, which have reported association of, improved nutritional status with ICDS services. [7,8,9,10]

As per WHO growth standards during 2012-13, 86% of children were weighted in the age group of 0-5 yrs. Of these mild, moderate underweight and severe underweight children are 59%, 38% and 3% respectively. [11,12] Very few studies are there with respect to nutritional status of children enrolled in Nandyal. So the present study is an attempt to assess the nutritional status of children availing services in anganwadi centres in rural Nandyal.

Objectives

1. To study the socio-demographic profile of children availing ICDS services in rural Nandyal.
2. To assess the nutritional status of pre-school children of age group 0-72 months enrolled in anganwadi centres of rural Nandyal.
3. To analyse the association of socio-demographic profile of children with nutritional status of children in anganwadi centres of rural Nandyal.

Material and Methods

The study is a community-based, observational, cross-sectional study.

Around 160 anganwadi centres are selected in rural area out of which 400 children registered in the anganwadi centres are enrolled from the records available with the centres, using Epi-info software. According to NFHS- 3 in Andhra Pradesh, 36.5% of children in age group of 0-36 months are under-nourished [13]

Sample size is determined using the following formula [14]

$$n = \frac{t^2 \times p \times q}{d^2}$$

Where: n = minimum sample size required

- t = confidence (for 95% of confidence interval, using 1.96)
- d = precision (5%)
- p = prevalence of under nutrition, which is 36.5%
- q = 100 - p, i.e 100-36.5% = 63.5%

Substituting the values,

$$\text{Sample size } n = \frac{1.96 \times 1.96 \times 0.365 \times 0.635}{0.05 \times 0.05}$$

$$n = \frac{0.8903}{0.0025} = 356.1$$

Thus, the minimum sample size needed for the study is 356.1

But to increase the validity around 400 children from rural anganwadi centres are selected for the study.

Twenty five children in the age group of 0-72 months are selected from each anganwadi centre using sample random sampling technique i.e. by lottery method after enlisting them from the anganwadi records from the area. Hence a total of 400 children from rural anganwadi centres are selected during the domiciliary visit and included for the study.

Study was done over a period of one year. A pre-designed, semi-structured questionnaire is developed and pilot study is done prior to the study.

Weight measurement is done by using Salter's weighing scale [14] which is a spring balance provided with the knickers to place the child (or) weighing scale to the nearest of 100grams with minimum of clothing and bare foot at the anganwadi centres. The Nutritional status of the selected children 0-72 months of age group is analyzed using height for age criterion using WHO child growth standards. Weight for age Z score was generated for the children according to WHO standards. The index of nutritional status that is weight for age, was expressed in standard deviation units (Z scores) from the reference median as

recommended by the WHO[15]

Z score is defined as:

$$\text{Z-score} = \frac{(\text{observed individual value} - \text{median value of the reference population})}{\text{Standard deviation of value in the reference population}}$$

Children who are below two standard deviation for reference medium (<-2 Z score) are considered to be under-nourished and who are below three standard deviation for reference medium (<-3 Z score) are considered to be severe malnourished. Children who are above two Z score values (>-2 Z score) are considered as normal.

Age of the child is recorded from the immunization card if available with the mother, or else from the health records available with the anganwadi workers.

Inclusion Criteria: ICDS beneficiaries who are registered with the anganwadi centres are included for the study.

Exclusion Criteria: The ICDS beneficiaries who are not registered with the anganwadi centres and those who came from other villages are excluded.

Statistical analysis: Simple proportions, percentages and chi square test are used to represent the data. SPSS statistical software version

26is used for analysis. WHO Anthro 2005, Anthroplus, Epi info version 7 statistical software is used for analysis.

The current WHO recommendation is to use the Z-Score or SD system to grade under nutrition [16].

Definitions of Variables: Children who are more than 2 SD above the reference median (i.e. a Z score of more than -2) are considered to be normal [16].

Under nutrition: Children who are more than 2 SD below the reference median (i.e. a Z-Score of less than -2) are considered to be undernourished i.e. to be stunted, wasted or to be underweight [16].

Severely malnourished: Children with measurements below 3 SD (a Z-Score of less than -3) are considered to be severely undernourished [16]

Ethical issues: Permission is taken from the CDPO, (Child Development Project Office) of Kurnool (at the time of study Nandyal was under Kurnool District) before beginning the study. Institutional Ethical Committee clearance was taken.

Results

Table 1: Socio-Demographic Profile of 0-72 Months Age Children

Variable	Number Of Children	
	Number	Percentage
Age		
≤12	72	18
12-24	84	21
25-36	93	23.2
37-48	47	11.7
49-60	53	13.2
61-72	51	12.7
Religion		
Hindus	362	90.5
Muslims	34	8.5
Christian	4	1
Literacy status of mother		
Illiterate	205	51.2
Primary and middle	107	26.8
Secondary and higher	75	18.8
Graduate and post graduate	4	1
Literacy status of Father		
Illiterate	205	51.2
Primary and middle	107	26.8
Secondary and higher	75	18.8
Graduate and post graduate	13	3.2
Socio –Economic Status		
I (Upper Class)	38	9.5
II (Upper Class)	38	12
III (Middle)	134	33.5
IV (Upper Lower)	122	30.5
V (Lower)	58	14.5
Total	400	100

In Table no.1, there are more number of children in the age group of 25-36 months (23.2%) when compared to 37-48 months (11.7%). With respect to religion Hindus accounted for 90.5% while Christians are less (1%). There are 54.5% illiterate mothers, and only 1% of graduates and post graduates.

Nearly half of the children’s parents are illiterate fathers (51.2%) and only 3.2% are graduates and post graduates. According to B.G. Prasad’s classification majority of the children belong to Middle class – III (33.5%) and only 9.5% belong to upper class – I.

Figure 1: Pie Diagram Showing Distribution of 0-72 Months Age Children According To Sex

This figure shows that there are 53% female and 47% male children.

Table 2: Distribution of Nutritional Status among 0-72 Months Age Children

Age(months)	Number of children (0-72 months)	Nutritional status					
		>-2 Z score (Normal)		<-2 Z score (under-nourished)		<-3 Z score (Severely Malnourished)	
		No	%	No	%	No	%
≤12	72	21	29.1	34	47.2	17	23.6
12-24	84	35	41.6	35	41.6	14	16.8
25-36	93	27	29.1	46	49.4	20	21.5
37-48	47	15	31.9	25	53.1	7	14.8
49-60	53	15	28.3	29	54.7	9	16.9
61-72	51	16	31.3	27	52.9	8	15.6
Total	400	129	32.2	196	49	75	18.8

Chi square (x²)=4.56 df=5 p>0.05

Infants (≤12 months) are comparatively less undernourished (47.2%) when compared to children in age group of 49-60 months (54.7%). There is more number of children in the age group of 12-24 months (41.6%) who are normal when compared to any other age group of children. Severity of malnutrition is more in infants (23.6%) when compared to any other age group of children. 49% of children are undernourished and 18.8% of children are severely malnourished. This is not statistically significant.

Table 3: Sex Wise Distribution of Nutritional Status among 0-72 Months Age Children

Sex	Number of children (0-72months)	Nutritional status					
		>-2 Z score (Normal)		<-2 Z score (under-nourished)		<-3 Z score (Severely Malnourished)	
		No	%	No	%	No	%
Males	188	54	29	95	50.5	39	20.5
Females	212	75	35.4	101	47.6	36	17
Total	400	129	32.3	196	49	75	18.7

Chi square (χ^2)=2.01 df=1 p>0.05

It is observed that males (50.5%) are more under nourished when compared with the females (47.6%) by WHO child growth standards. It is not statistically significant.

Figure 2: Bar Diagram Showing Sex Wise Distribution of Nutritional Status In Rural Area

Table 4: Age and Sex Wise Prevalence of under Nutrition (<-2 Z score)

Age (months)	Undernourished (<-2 Z score)								
	Males			Females			Total		
	Total	No	%	Total	No	%	Total	No	%
≤12	34	19	55.8	38	15	39.5	72	34	47.2
12-24	44	18	40.9	40	17	42.5	84	35	41.6
25-36	42	21	50	51	25	49	93	46	49.4
37-48	22	12	54.5	25	13	52	47	25	53.1
49-60	24	13	54.1	29	16	55.1	53	29	54.7
61-72	22	12	54.5	29	15	51.7	51	27	52.9
Total	188	95	50.5	212	101	47.6	400	196	49

Chi square (χ^2)=1.93 df=1 p>0.05

This table shows that there are 39.5% of female infants undernourished when compared to male infants (55.8%), but it is not statistically significant.

Table 5: Distribution of Nutritional Status of 0-72 Months Age Children According to Religion

Religion	Number of children (0-72months)	Nutritional status					
		>-2 Z score (Normal)		<-2 Z score (under-nourished)		<-3 Z score (Severely Malnourished)	
		No	%	No	%	No	%
Hindus	362	113	30.9	179	49.5	70	19.6
Muslims	34	13	38.2	16	47	5	14.8
Christians	4	3	75	1	25	0	0
Total	400	129	32.3	196	49	75	18.7

Chi square (χ^2)=4.08 df=2 p>0.05

This table shows that there are 25% Christians, 49.5% Hindus and 47% Muslims are undernourished. Hindus (19.6%) are more severely malnourished when compared to Muslims (14.8%). This is not statistically significant.

Figure 3: Bar Diagram Showing Distribution of Children According to Nutritional Status

This figure shows that there are 49% undernourished while 18.8% severely malnourished children.

Table 6: Distribution of the Nutritional Status of 0-72 Months Age Group of Children According to Literacy Status of Mother

Literacy status of mother	Number of children (0-72months)	Number of Children					
		>-2 Z score (Normal)		<-2 Z score (under-nourished)		<-3 Z score (Severely Malnourished)	
		No	%	No	%	No	%
Illiterate	218	60	30.3	116	50.4	42	19.3
Primary and middle	98	32	32.6	46	46.9	20	20.5
Secondary and higher secondary	80	34	42.5	33	41.3	13	16.2
Graduate and post graduate	4	3	75	1	25	0	0
Total	400	129	32.3	196	49	75	18.7

Chi square (χ^2)=4.8 df=1 p<0.05 literate vs. illiterate

This table shows that there are more number of children who are under nourished among literate mothers (50.4%) than children among graduate and post graduate mother (25%). There is more number of children (20.5%) in primary and middle class

level of education among mothers who are severely malnourished. There are 75% of normal grades of children among graduates and post graduates when compared to 30.3% among literate mothers. This is statistically significant.

Table 7: Distribution of the Nutritional Status of 0-72 Months Age Group of Children According to Literacy Status of Father

Literacy status of father	Number of children (0-72months)	Number of Children					
		>-2 Z score (Normal)		<-2 Z score (under-nourished)		<-3 Z score (Severely Malnourished)	
		No	%	No	%	No	%
Illiterate	205	59	28.8	102	49.7	44	21.6
Primary and middle	107	33	30.8	52	48.5	22	20.5
Secondary and higher secondary	75	30	40	37	49.3	8	10.7
Graduate and post graduate	13	7	54	5	38.4	1	7.6
Total	400	129	32.3	196	49	75	18.7

Chi square (χ^2)=2.3 df=1 p>0.05 literate vs. illiterate

This table shows that there is more number of children (21.6%) who are severely malnourished among literate fathers than any other group of children whose fathers are literates. But this is not statistically significant.

Discussion

As per 2011 census [2] the sex ratio among children (0-6 years) is 919 i.e there are 919 females per 1000 males in India.

According to census of India 2011[2], Hinduism accounted for 79.80% of the population of India. Islam 14.23%, Christianity 2.30% and Sikhism 1.72% are the other major religions followed by the people of India. According to the 2011 census, Andhra Pradesh has an overall literacy rate of 67.66%. The male literacy rate is 75.56% and the female literacy rate is 59.74%.

Infants (≤ 12 months) are comparatively less undernourished (47.2%) when compared to children in age group of 49-60 months (54.7%). There are more number of children in the age group of 12-24 months (41.6%) who are normal when compared to any other age group of children. Severity of malnutrition is more in infants (23.6%) when compared to any other age group of children. 49% of children are undernourished and 18.8% of children are severely malnourished. This is not statistically significant. Dongre A R et al [17] found that the prevalence of underweight significantly increased with age and peaked at age of 12-23 months where it was 61%.

It is observed that males (50.5%) are more undernourished when compared with the females (47.6%) by WHO child growth standards. It is not statistically significant. Ray SK et al[18] in their study on rapid assessment of nutritional status and dietary pattern found that there are more number of males (64.74%) who are malnourished than females (51.58%). The findings are similar with Deshmukh PR et al [] study which found that boys were slightly more likely to be underweight (54%) than girls (52%).

This study shows that there are 39.5% of female infants undernourished when compared to male infants (55.8%), but it is not statistically significant. There is a gradual increase in prevalence of under nutrition among females from ≤ 12 months (39.5%) to 49-60 months (55.1%) age group of children. Overall there is less prevalence of under nutrition in age group of 12-24 months (41.6%) when compared to any other age group of children.

These findings are similar to that of N. seetharaman et al[19] where they found that female infants (46.9%) are having significantly lower prevalence of under nutrition when compared to male infants (86.1%). In the present study there are more number of children who are undernourished among literate mothers (50.4%) than children among graduate and post graduate mother (25%). There are more number of children (20.5%) in primary and middle class level of education among mothers who are severely malnourished. There are 75% of normal grades of children among graduates and post graduates when compared to 30.3% among literate mothers. This is statistically significant. Harishankar et al [20] found that there are 2.8% of children of severely malnourished among literate mothers while compared to no children of severely malnourished in literate mothers.

In the present study there are more number of children (21.6%) who are severely malnourished among literate fathers than any other group of children whose fathers are literates. But this is not statistically significant. The findings are similar with the following study. Ray SK et al[18] found that there was substantial differences in the prevalence of malnutrition when observed among children belonging to literate fathers (74.6%) and illiterate fathers (57.28%) which was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$).

Bhat IA et al, in their study for impact of sociomedical factors on the nutritional status of preschool children in an urban setting of Srinagar noticed that parental literacy was associated with preschool child malnutrition.[21] The present study also showed the similar association of nutritional

status with respect to mother's literacy ($p < 0.05$).

Bhalani KD et al [22], in their study in vadodacity, found that more than 60% of infants were found normal against 37.6% of children 1 to 2 years, 29.3% of children 2 to 3 years, 23.5% of children of 3 years and above ($p < 0.0001$), whereas in the present study more than half of the undernourished children (54.7%) belong to 49-60 months age.

Mishra V.K et al [23], in their study on women's education can improve child nutrition in India found that, based on standards developed by the WHO, 52% of children under age 4 years are stunted, 17% were wasted, and 54% were underweight. Maternal education has the strongest independent influence on child malnutrition. Children whose mothers have little or no education tend to have a lower nutritional status than do children of more educated mothers similar to the present study.

Pathak PK], in his study found that 41.8% of Hindu children, 39.9% of Muslim children were undernourished. Males (41.4%) were more undernourished when compared to females (40.7%). [24], This study findings are very similar to the present study in which Hindu children account for 49.5% of under nutrition and 47% of muslim children account for malnutrition. Regarding the gender variation, males (50.5%) are more undernourished than females (47.6%). Hence the present study indicates more research to find out the causes related to improper nutritional status among children in spite of the enormous efforts put forth by the government's flagship ICDS programme.

Limitations:

1. Only weight for height criteria was used to estimate the nutritional status of children.
2. ICDS beneficiaries who are registered with the anganwadi centre are selected as the study groups so there is a chance of selection bias.

Conclusion

Males are comparatively more undernourished (50.5%) than females (47.6%) according to WHO child growth standards. Christians are less undernourished (25%) when compared to Hindus (49.5%) and Muslims (47%).

Children of illiterate mothers (50.4%) are more undernourished when compared to children of graduate and post graduate mothers (25%).

Recommendations

Various activities like home visits, street plays, door to door visits, etc. should be organized on regular basis with active participation of local NGOs or Mahila Mandals in the village. Motivation of both mother and father should be considered

with regard to nutrition of children by the Anganwadi workers.

A periodic evaluation of the ongoing ICDS programme should be taken into consideration. It is also imperative to introduce the new WHO Growth standards in the ICDS scheme as early as possible which will help in a more effective monitoring of growth pattern and can be used to compare data on national and international levels.

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